

PREDICTION OF PERMEABILITY FOR THREE DIMENSIONAL CIRCULAR BRAIDED PREFORM

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SUMMARY: Complete prediction of second order permeability tensor for three dimensional circular braided preform is critical to understand the resin transfer molding process of composites. The permeability can be predicted by considering resin flow through the multi-axial fiber structure. In this study, permeability tensor for a 3-D circular braided preform is calculated by solving a boundary problem of a periodic unit cell. Flow field through the unit cell is obtained by using a 3-D finite volume method (FVM) and Darcy's law is utilized to obtain permeability tensor. Flow analysis for two cases that a fiber tow is regarded as an impermeable solid and as a permeable porous medium is carried out respectively. It is found that the flow within the intra-tow region of the braided preform is negligible if inter-tow porosity is relatively high but the flow through the tow must be considered when the porosity is low. To avoid checkerboard pressure field and improve the efficiency of numerical computation, a new interpolation function for velocity variation is proposed on the basis of analytic solutions. Permeability of the braided preform is measured through a radial flow experiment and compared with the permeability predicted numerically.

KEYWORDS: permeability, braided preform, resin transfer molding (RTM), finite volume method, porous media

INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) is an efficient and frequently used process for producing fiber reinforced polymer composites which have either small simple shape or large complex shape. Determination of permeability is essential in design and practical application of the process and the permeability can be determined by various methods, e.g., experimental measurement, analytical computation, and numerical prediction. Darcy's law is expressed by the following equation.

$$\mathbf{u} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \cdot \nabla P \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the volume averaged velocity vector of the resin, μ is the Newtonian viscosity of fluid, ∇P is the pressure gradient vector, and \mathbf{K} is the permeability tensor of porous medium.

The experimental measurement often requires a large number of carefully controlled experiments. The analytical prediction computed by the Kozeny-Carman equation is very simple but has weakness with strongly anisotropic preforms. As a consequence, many efforts have been conducted to numerically predict the permeability for the past few years. But most of them have been carried out for infinitely long unidirectional preforms which are not used frequently for the resin transfer molding[1-9]. Recently, simplified permeability models for a woven fabric have been studied but the unit cell was simplified too much and either lubrication theory or one dimensional flow was applied.

In this study, permeability tensor is computed for a three dimensional braided preform by applying a FVM to a unit cell. It is evident that resin will flow through the inter-tow and the intra-tow regions when pressure gradient is applied to the resin. The intra-tow region in the

braided preform is regarded as not only an impermeable solid but also a permeable porous media. When the intra-tow region is regarded as the impermeable solid and excluded from domain of flow analysis, the Stokes equation is computed for the inter-tow region. In the case of the porous media, the Stokes and the Brinkman equations are used to calculate flow field in the inter-tow and intra-tow regions, respectively. In order to obtain the permeability experimentally, a radial flow test is performed and the results are compared with numerically predicted values.

GEOMETRIC MODELING

The braided preform is produced by using a 3-D circular braiding machine which has the compressed air mode and 1×1 machine pattern. 3-D circular braiding process is composed of two motions, beating and step motions. The beating motion makes the structure of yarn more solid-like by compacting the yarns in axis direction and the step motion comprises four steps to obtain the same arrangement of carriers. Based on the carrier motion, a geometric modeling is conducted. The braiding machine is composed of 12 carriers in radial direction and 48 carriers in circumferential direction, i.e., 12×48 preform patterns are available. But 7×48 carriers are used in this study. The braided preform has a geometrical structure repeated per pitch length along cylindrical mandrel axis and the repeated structure again consists of the same 24 unit cells in the circumferential direction. As 7 carriers exist in the radial direction on the machine bed, each unit cell comprises 7 sub-unit cells, that is, 5 inner unit cells and 2 surface unit cells. Figure 1 shows the unit cell which is composed of the sub-unit cells.

Fig. 1. Curved unit cell including sub-unit cells for 3-D circular braided preform.

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Most of the previous studies have used straight lines describe yarn paths in the unit cell of the braided preform. In this work, however, the yarn paths are described as curved spline functions which are close to

real geometry of the 3-D braided preform. In order to calculate permeabilities by using the numerical method, a curved unit cell is flattened as shown in Fig. 2. This transformation is acceptable because diameter of mandrel is relatively large, that is, 80 mm. Cross-section of the yarn is assumed to be elliptic based on real yarn geometry.

Fig. 2. Transformation of (a) curved unit cell into (b) flattened unit cell when the unit cell is described in the x-z plane perpendicular to the mandrel direction.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Governing equations

In this study, flow in the inter-tow region is governed by both the continuity and the Stokes equations as follows.

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} = \nabla p \quad (3)$$

As the tow of the braided preform is treated as a permeable porous medium, the flow within intra-tow region is modeled by using the Brinkman equation given by

$$\mu_e \nabla^2 \langle \mathbf{u} \rangle - \mu \mathbf{K}^{-1} \cdot \langle \mathbf{u} \rangle = \nabla \langle p \rangle \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{K}^{-1} is the permeability tensor for the fiber tow and $\langle \rangle$ means volume an averaged value. μ_e is the viscosity used in the porous medium. In order to examine contribution of the flow to the overall flow rate through intra-tow region, the tow is also regarded as impermeable solid and the intra-tow region is excluded in the domain of the flow analysis. It is assumed that μ is equal to μ_e . Because the Brinkman equation contains permeability tensor of the intra-tow region, the permeability tensor is obtained from numerical flow analysis for the micro-unit cell which represents periodic structure of filaments inside the tow. The filaments are thought to be arranged in the hexagonal array because it is more acceptable than quadratic array. As the braided preform is compacted under pressure, the permeability of the intra-tow region is also varied as a function of intra-tow porosity. The permeability tensor of the intra-tow region is transversely isotropic with respect to the plane perpendicular to filament axis but each axis of many filaments doesn't accord with the direction of global flow along which pressure gradient is imposed. The coordinate transformation between each direction of the tow composed of filaments and the direction of global flow is needed to be conducted by using the basis of direction vectors as follows.

$$\mathbf{K}_G = \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{K}_L \mathbf{T} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{K}_G represents the permeability tensor for the direction of global flow, global coordinate frame and \mathbf{T} is the transformation matrix obtained from direction vectors and \mathbf{K}_L is permeability tensor for the direction of the tow in local coordinate frame. The Brinkman equation needs to utilize the permeability tensor for global coordinate frame as an input.

Numerical method

The control volume finite element method (CVFEM) is used in order to compute flow field. Differential equations can be cast in the following general forms.

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = S \quad (6)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{g} = 0 \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{J} is a diffusion flux, S is a source term, and \mathbf{g} is a mass flux vector, $\rho \mathbf{v}$.

By applying appropriate conservation principles to a control volume, integral forms of the equations (6) and (7) can be obtained as follows.

$$\int_{\partial V} \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds = \int_V S dV \quad (8)$$

$$\int_{\partial V} \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds = 0 \quad (9)$$

where ∂V is the surface of control volume, and \mathbf{n} is the outward unit vector normal to a differential area, ds .

If velocity and pressure values were stored at the same grid points and interpolated by similar functions, the resulting discretized equations could experience physically unrealistic checkerboard type pressure fields. In the present study, a novel interpolation function for velocity field is used to enhance the efficiency of numerical computation. The velocity and pressure fields are interpolated within each control volume as the follows.

$$u = A^u x + B^u y + C^u z + D^u - \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \left[x - \frac{1}{4}(y^2 + z^2) \right] \quad (10)$$

$$v = A^v x + B^v y + C^v z + D^v - \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \left[y - \frac{1}{4}(z^2 + x^2) \right] \quad (11)$$

$$w = A^w x + B^w y + C^w z + D^w - \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \left[z - \frac{1}{4}(x^2 + y^2) \right] \quad (12)$$

$$p = A^p x + B^p y + C^p z + D^p \quad (13)$$

Discretized equations are obtained by substituting above equations into the control volume integral equations and assembling them appropriately. Contribution of the boundary conditions is also calculated and included in the following discretized equations.

$$a_i^u u_i = \sum_n a_n^u u_n + c_i^u + \sum_n \lambda_n^u p_n \quad (14)$$

$$a_i^v v_i = \sum_n a_n^v v_n + c_i^v + \sum_n \lambda_n^v p_n \quad (15)$$

$$a_i^w w_i = \sum_n a_n^w w_n + c_i^w + \sum_n \lambda_n^w p_n \quad (16)$$

$$a_i^p p_i = \sum_n a_n^p p_n + b_i^p \quad (17)$$

where i is a typical node and n represents neighboring nodes around i .

The above discretized equations yield coupled set of algebraic equations and are solved simultaneously by using iteration solvers. When the proper limit of convergence can not be obtained, a corresponding under-relaxation method is used as a means of settlement.

Flow analysis for unit cell

When the tow is regarded as a permeable porous medium, flow simulation is performed simultaneously for both the inter-tow and intra-tow regions within a unit cell shown in Fig. 3. But in the case that the tow is thought as an impermeable solid, the flow analysis domain is only the inter-tow region and the flow simulation is carried out for the region.

Fig. 3. Geometrical structure of flattened unit including sub-unit cells.

A single tow is composed of about 9000 filaments whose diameter is about $9 \mu\text{m}$. As the braided preform is compacted, both the intra-tow and the inter-tow porosities are varied. Three dimensional numerical analysis is carried out for the flow along the plane and the flow perpendicular to the plane of the unit cell by using the CVFEM described above. When the braided preform is compacted, minor axis of elliptic cross-section in the unit cell is reduced while the major axis is assumed to be constant. The governing equations, the Stokes equation and the Brinkman equation, can be solved by assuming appropriate boundary conditions for the in-plane flow and for the flow perpendicular to the plane. Pressure is imposed at the inlet and the outlet planes of the unit cell and periodic boundary conditions are given along the planes. It is also assumed that velocity is zero on tow surfaces. The velocity and pressure fields are obtained for the unit cell and total flow rate, Q , is calculated for each direction. Then the permeability, K , for each direction of the unit cell is obtained through the following equation.

$$K = \frac{Q\mu}{A\Delta p} \quad (18)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area including both fluid and fibers. As a result, the second order permeability tensor for the braided preform is obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

The in-plane permeability of the braided preform is measured experimentally with the radial flow method, which can prevent edge effect. However, the permeability perpendicular to the braided preform is not determined experimentally because it is hard to measure the flow rate across the thickness of the braided layer. The radial mold is designed to be able to change the thickness of mold cavity easily and to maintain the inlet pressure at a constant level. The permeability is measured by observing the advancement of flow front during filling. The 3-D circular braided preform shown in Fig. 4 is made out of S-2 glass roving yarns (Advance Glassfiber Yarns, LLC).

Fig. 4. Circular braided glass preform prepared and used in the experiment.

The shape

braided preform is a hollow circular cylinder because of the of cylindrical mandrel but the mold cavity is designed to fit a thin rectangular plate. In order to place the preform into the flat mold cavity the circular braided preform is stitched, cut and flattened. The braided preform is spread with the assumption that the geometrical structure is not altered significantly during unfolding. The fluid used for the experiment is a silicone oil (dimethyl siloxane polymer, DC 200F/100CS, from Dow Corning) with the viscosity of 9.7×10^{-2} Pa·s. The silicone oil shows the Newtonian behavior so that Darcy's law can be applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows pressure contours in the unit cell of the braided preform when the pressure gradient is imposed as the boundary condition along the y-direction and the tow is treated as porous medium. The velocity and pressure distributions obtained from the numerical calculation are used to predict the permeability tensor of the braided preform with the equation (18). Based on the experimental results, principal directions of the permeability tensor are determined as the x, y, and z directions of the unit cell, which are circumferential, mandrel axis, and thickness directions of the preform. As the braided preform is compacted under the applied pressure in the mold, thickness and porosity of the preform are reduced.

Fig. 5. Pressure contours within the unit cell for the resin flow in y axis direction by considering the intra-two flow.

The permeability for each principal direction is obtained numerically with respect to the entire porosity as shown in Fig. 6. The permeabilities predicted for

two cases that yarns are porous media and impermeable solids are compared. The permeability increases with the increase in the entire porosity and the permeability for y direction has the highest value. The results are explained if geometrical architecture is examined. Because the average yarn orientation angle from the mandrel axis is 26° , the flow in y direction will be dominant. The contribution of the intra-tow flow to the permeability tensor (e.g., intra-tow permeability) can be neglected if the entire porosity is above about 0.6. In this case, it is sufficiently accurate that the tow is regarded as impermeable solid and is numerically much efficient. When the porosity is low, the permeabilities for thickness direction of the preform are different in two cases considering the tow as porous medium and solid. Therefore, the flow through the tow along the direction of thickness is important at low porosity and must be taken into account. The predicted permeability is compared with the experimental results as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Measured and calculated permeabilities with respect to porosity.

When the thickness of the mold cavity is reduced much to achieve high fiber volume fraction, it is difficult to generate an FE mesh owing to high compaction and geometrical complexity, and large deformation of the transparent top plate of the mold is observed. Therefore, both the numerical prediction and experimental measurements are performed for the porosity higher than 50 %. There are some discrepancies between numerical and experimental results in the case of x direction. The differences may be attributed to the nesting and shifting effects of the layers between sub-unit cells, distortion of the unit cell during flattening the cylindrical preform, and coarseness of the FE mesh. When the entire porosity is 69 % and pitch length of the braided preform is 0.02 m, the second order permeability tensor calculated by using the Brinkman equation is given as follows.

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.912 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1.352 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.512 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \quad (19)$$

As shown by the permeability tensor, off-diagonal components are zero because axes of the local coordinate system are coincident with the principal directions of the permeability tensor. If a permeability tensor in a specific direction were needed in order to predict the resin flow through the preform, it could be obtained through coordinate transformation of the tensor by

Fig. 6. Comparison of permeabilities predicted for each direction as a function of porosity.

using basis vectors. In order to estimate the effect of variations in pressure and viscosity on the permeability, the pressure difference between the inlet and outlet planes and the viscosity are varied. As the result, it is observed that the permeability is independent of variations in pressure difference and viscosity, and is only a function of the unit cell structure.

CONCLUSIONS

Geometric modeling is carried out to construct the unit cell for the 3-D circular braided preform. Unlike previous studies, this work is based on the three dimensional unit cell in which the curved elliptic yarn is taken into account. In order to obtain the permeability numerically, the three dimensional flow analysis is performed for the unit cell by assuming two cases that yarns are porous media and impermeable solids, respectively. It is found that the flow within the intra-tow region of braided preform is negligible if inter-tow porosity is relatively high but the flow through the tow, especially for the direction of thickness, must be considered when the porosity is low. In the case of relatively high porosity, the assumption that the tow is regarded as impermeable solid considerably reduces numerical hardship like calculation time and memory requirement. The numerically predicted permeability tensor of the braided preform is compared with experimental values which are measured from radial flow experiment. The calculated permeability is higher than the measured value and the permeability in the machine direction of the preform is the highest among three directions. The discrepancy may result from geometrical complexity such as nesting and shifting effects and deformation of the unit cell in the flattening process.

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REFERENCES

1. Sangani AS, Acrivos A. Slow flow through a periodic array of spheres. *Int J Multiphase Flow* 1982; 8(4): 343-360.
2. Gebart BR. Permeability of unidirectional reinforcements for RTM. *J Comp Mat* 1992; 26(8): 1100-1133.
3. Skartsis L, Khomai B, Kardos JL. Resin flow through fiber beds during composite manufacturing processes. Part II: numerical and experimental studies of Newtonian flow through ideal and actual fiber beds. *Poly Eng Sci* 1992; 32(4): 231-239.
4. Berdichevsky AL, Cai Z. Preform permeability predictions by self-consistent method and finite element simulation. *Poly Comp* 1993; 14(2): 132-143.
5. Cai Z, Berdichevsky AL. Estimation of the resin flow permeability of fiber tow preforms using the self-consistent method. *Poly Comp* 1993; 15(3): 240-246.
6. Papathanasiou TD. On the effective permeability of square arrays of permeable fiber tows. *Int J Multiphase Flow* 1997; 23(1): 81-92.
7. Papathanasiou TD, Gravel EM, Barwick SC, Dendy ED. Non-isotropic structured fibrous media: the permeability of arrays of fiber bundles of elliptical cross section. *Poly Comp* 2002; 23(4): 520-529.
8. Choi MA, Lee MH, Chang J, Lee SJ. Permeability modeling of fibrous media in composite processing. *J Non-Newtonian Fluid Mech* 1998; 79: 585-598.
9. Phelan FRJr, Wise G. Analysis of transverse flow in aligned fibrous porous media. *Comp Part A* 1996; 27: 25-34.
10. Ranganathan S, Phelan FRJr, Advani SG. A generalized model for the transverse fluid permeability in unidirectional fibrous media. *Poly Comp* 1996; 17(2): 222-230.
11. Nedanov PB, Advani SG. Numerical computation of the fiber preform permeability tensor by the homogenization method. *Poly Comp* 2002; 23(5): 758-770.

12. Šimáček P, Advani SG. Permeability model for a woven fabric. *Poly Comp* 1996; 17(6): 887-899.
13. Yu B, Lee J. A simplified in-plane permeability model for textile fabrics. *Poly Comp* 2000; 21(5): 660-685.
14. Ngo ND, Tamma KK. Microscale permeability predictions of porous fibrous media. *Int J Heat and Mass Transfer* 2001; 44: 3135-3145.